

AN ANTHROPOLOGICAL INVESTIGATION OF GENDER ROLES IN IBIBIO TRADITIONAL MARRIAGE PRACTICE

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ABSTRACT

Marriage is a union that makes the creation of man and a woman reasonably enjoyable despite the fact that different culture has its influence on what marriage should be within the context a cultural belief system. Gender roles defined man's ability and woman's position especially within a patriarchal society like the Ibibio society. This qualitative research examined the changes in gender roles in Ibibio marriage practices. Gender Conflict Theory was adopted as theoretical framework. Ethnographic methodology with Fetterman's big-net approach was adopted for the study. Study participants were purposively selected to be married men and women or those who have experienced marriage within the context of Ibibio marriage practice. Snowballing technique and respondents driven technique were adopted to reach study participants. Four local government areas which include Etinan, Ibesikpo-Asutan, Ikono and Uruan, which cut across the 3 senatorial district of Akwa Ibom State, were engaged in the study. Findings of the study show that women are becoming bread-winners which were traditionally ascribed for men in Ibibio traditional marriage practice, men are participating in house chores which were ascribed for women in traditional Ibibio marriage practice, and leadership roles are being shared among married couples today against what was traditionally men dominance in Ibibio traditional marriage practice. Among others, research recommend that married couples should understand marriage as a union which anyone should be able to help when the needs arises provided there is capacity to do so.

KEYWORDS: Marriage, Ibibio, Bread-winner, House chores, Leadership and culture

INTRODUCTION

Marriage is the legal union of a man and woman as husband and wife, and according to Crane (2014), in some jurisdictions it is between two persons of the same sex, usually

entailing legal obligations of each person to the other. Crane further posits that this definition is being disputed by some states because of the inclusion of, “two persons of the same sex”. Among the Christians' behavioural belief system, it includes a spiritual component to marriage for example, the Christian faith's use of Matthew 19:4-6 (King James Version) as a definition stating, “For this cause (marriage) shall a man leave father and mother, and shall cleave to his wife: and they twain shall be one flesh.” However, 1 Kings 11:2 states that King Solomon had 700 wives deviating from the two person component of the definition. Marriage is a relationship between a man and a woman with expected roles which are culturally, biologically and socially defined (Crane, 2014; Paul and Peters, 2023). These expected roles have change over the years with changes in the contextual definition of what marriage is. These roles are also relative with varieties of cultural practices and beliefs. These roles are based on what is termed sex and gender. Gender differences in term of man and woman are determinant factors to creation of expected roles which are accorded to man and woman as husband and wife, and these expectations varies from one cultural ethnic group to another. According to Ercan and Ucar (2021), marriage and expectations from marriage can be seen as a contractual obligation that is designed to gain social, cultural and financial gains, as well as a personal choice designed to strengthen the bond between two people dominated by romantic intimacy.

Gender roles are a set of social and behavioral norms that, within a specific culture, are widely considered to be socially appropriate for individuals of a specific sex (n. d. 2023). The perception of gender roles includes attitudes, actions and personality traits associated with a particular sex within specific culture. Every marriage create certain expectations from the society that conceives these expectations as gender roles. Gender roles are predominantly considered within a family context as well as within society (n. d. 2023). According to Williams and McBrain (2006), gender roles are typically determined by the society. According to the United State of America National Healthy Marriage Resource Centre Fact Sheet (2009), gender roles and expectations play a significant role in couple interaction, family decision-making, and perspectives on marital satisfaction. As society or cultural group creates gender roles, they preserve it through socialization by institutionalizing the process of socialization from generation to generation. It has been observed that appropriate gender behaviours of women and men that are learned during socialization process mostly are associated with gender stereotypical beliefs which are rooted in patriarchal societies; they are transferred through the socialization factors to next generation (n. d. 2023).

In patriarchal societies, gender roles are created and transferred in reference to man's ability and woman's ability as perceived by the society. This is also a determinant factor in marriage within the society, and marital roles are perceived, appreciated from this perspective, in such a way that some forms of deviants are frowned at by members of the society. The dynamic nature of culture has brought changes in the traditional settings even within the patriarchal society. Patriarchy is not a constant and gender relations which are dynamic and complex have changed over the periods of history (n. d. 2023). Women in this form of society are placed under the control of men. The nature of control and subjugation of women varies from one society to the other as it differs due to the differences in class, caste, religion, region, ethnicity and the socio-cultural practice.

Current economics have contributed to changes in marriage and gender roles among

married couples, whereby most couples earn their living separately, rather than from a jointly run family business (Crane, 2014). According to Coontz (2006), the situation has provided more independence and an easier transition into living separate lives if things get difficult, and this also impacts the expectations of marriage. There have been changes in the gender roles among married couples across the world and this is relative to states and culture. Changes in gender roles affect the man's roles and the woman's roles with the couples focusing on the survival and progress within the economic structure and situation as related to the state or nation. Women have taken to work in order to compliment the financial needs of the couples and men may now be needed in the home more because he is no longer the only person working (Crane, 2014) in order to keep the family at success level. Chores and child rearing are no longer exclusively female responsibilities, as household responsibilities are more equal with no real defining lines on what is the male or female expectation, causing more gender role confusion (Crane, 2014). These changes are transient from one society to another.

Ibibio people of Akwa Ibom State in southern Nigeria are found within a patriarchal society structure. This kind of society has women under the control and leadership of men, and gender roles are created accordingly. Literatures like "Gender Roles Socialization in Patriarchy Society" by (n. d. 2023) has reported that women in this kind of society are culturally placed under the control of men, and the nature of this control and subjugation varies from one society to the other as it differs due to the differences in class, caste, religion, region, ethnicity and the socio-cultural practice. Among the Ibibio people of Southern Nigeria, socialization of gender roles is to distinguish between men and women. This differentiation characterized every aspect of the Ibibio society including marriage among the people.

Among the married couples in Ibibio land, gender roles are traditionally defined and these definitions clearly draw the moral lines for what is culturally acceptable and what is considered to be deviant among married couples. Since marriage is a cultural practice and according to Modo (2016) culture is dynamic, the emergence of modernization and changes in economic situations has brought about several kinds of changes which have also affected gender roles among married couples in Ibibio land. The changes have crawl into the society in such a way that the moral boundaries are becoming every thin in order for the people to consider some of these changes as deviants even when it is traditionally stated or coded to have been deviance. The changes in gender roles among married couples especially in the rural areas of Ibibio land is becoming contextual as these have brought about divisions among the people. In the Ibibio society today, women are effectively playing roles that were ascribed for husbands, fathers, brothers and sons. This has brought about certain degree of conflict especially in recent marriages among the Ibibio people. Modern couples are faced with the challenge of adopting the changes in order to make their marriages work or maintaining the traditional patriarchal status-quo of men's dominance in order to satisfy the expectations of the Ibibio society. Based on this background, the researcher decided to examine the changes in gender roles as perceived by married couples among Ibibio people of Akwa Ibom State, Southern Nigeria.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Conflict Theory in Gender

According to Balgar (2018), conflict theory can be held as a struggle between dominant group which has the tool of production and working class which is exploited by a dominant group. Karl Marx is the father of conflict theory and his colleague Friederich Engel moved this idea and applied to the family structure and the household. According to his view, relationship that between exploiter and exploited also exist in household in families. He differentiate modern and pre-modern societies in a way that men and women roles. In pre-modern societies, there was no big difference between the two gender and because there was no reason considered for exploiting one and the other. Contrary, in modern societies, there is private property right and this right is transmitting by patriarchy. So, he says that there was no inequality in hunter and gatherer societies, inequality is a characteristic of a capitalist system. In modern societies, because women are not paid for their house works, their works began to be seen as unnecessary, and men show themselves as bread winner (Balgar, 2018).

METHODOLOGY

Ethnographic research design was adopted by the researcher for the study. This research design involves multiple qualitative data collection techniques such as in-depth interview, key informant interview, focus group discussion and objective observation by the researcher. The study was conducted in four Ibibio local government areas across Akwa Ibom State. Etinan Local Government Area, Ibessikpo-Asutan Local Government Area, Ikono Local Government Area and Uruan Local Government Area were selected for the study. Two villages were randomly selected from each of the four selected local government areas.

The researcher through Fetterman (2010) big-net approach randomly selects study participants from one village per local government area. The researcher randomly select study participants who co-operated, and were ready to give answers to the questions as were required. Method of data collection include interview, participant observation and key informant interview. Instrument for data collection was and interview guide which was used by the researcher and his three research assistants. Data were analysed thematically with excerpts from the narratives of the study participants.

RESULTS

Gender Role relatively to Bread-Winner among the Ibibio Married Couples

Gathered narratives show that among the Ibibio married couples in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, the issue of who should be or who is a bread-winner (that is the person who takes care of financial responsibilities) has change from what was traditional though the traditional patterns still remains within the cultural norms of the people. Modernization is believed to have exerted great change in the gender roles among married couples in Ibibio land. Some of the study participants in their narratives attested to the fact that there are changes from the traditional pattern in bread-winner as a gender role among married couples. One of the key informants' participants in her narratives explained that:

Men were traditionally accepted to be the bread-winners in the past and may

be it was because of the nature of the society then which made everybody sought after male children and my mother and her mates then were on hot seat anytime a man wants to marry them because the society wanted them to give birth to male children who will end up becoming the bread-winner for his family and the extended family. But you can see that things have change and today, a lot of women are taking care of their husband and their children. In fact, so many women today do not depend on men because they can provide bread for themselves, their children, their parents and other siblings. Thank God for civilization that brought us enlightenment that allowed women to go to school and get employment, and earned their salaries. Even in the market sector; *ha ha ha, ...*(laughs), we women have occupied the space and men are struggling to compete with us in the market. My brothers, things have changed and the issue of who is a bread-winner has died. And I want to tell my fellow women, if you are still waiting for a man to come and marry you and take care of everything for you, you will not marry because even men know that things have changed (Female, 56 years, business woman, interviewed on 24th July, 2023).

Changes in the society have influenced gender roles among the Ibibio married couples in Akwa Ibom State. Gathered information revealed that the traditional status-quo of patriarchal dominance in the society which placed men as bread-winners is undergoing continuous change among some sets of the Ibibio people even as there are some others who are still upholding the tradition of dependency on men. One of the study participants in his narratives explained that;

The computer age has brought us so much change in our society today in such a way that what we used to believe that it was right, but today there are so many adjustments. In term of who is or should be a bread-winner among a married couple, I can say that within some classes of people, there is a belief system no woman should depend on any man and this has to do with the rich class. This is so because they are capable of sending their female children to school. But within the poor class who have no money to send their girl child too far in education, they still want their daughters to get married to a rich man who will be able to provide for and her children. So there is a change no doubt, but these changes exist in categories and in class. I know that the change has greatly influenced our society such that few girls do not want to depend on men anymore as bread-winners. But the majority still carry it as our culture in such a way that even when they are working to earn their living, they still believe that it is our tradition for men to take care of women as their bread-winners (Male, 60 years, trader, interviewed on 24th July, 2023)

Gender role has been culturally created by the Ibibio people of Akwa Ibom State. Gathered data revealed that the culture of the people influenced the roles ascribed to men and women which are relative to marriage as well. Among the Ibibio ethnic group, gender role in term of providing financially to the family has been ascribed to men as tradition and this has determined the setting of the society. Marriage is structured in the said tradition which is evidence in the payment of bride price which positioned the man as the gender who is responsible for creating a family and must be ready to take care of the financial burden of the

family he created. According to a study participant from Etinan;

Men were bread-winners from time immemorial especially among us here. You can see how it was structured; that a man is expected to be ready to take care of every financial burden of his family before he can say he wants to get married. In fact, if you don't have any income or something that is giving you money, you cannot talk about marriage here else, and the society looks at you as a fool. Even you very own family will not want to accompany you to the bride's family because they don't want the society to blame them if you fail in financial responsibility as bread winner. They don't want to be your burden bearer because they will think that your wife will be coming to them for help due to your inability to provide for her. So men are traditionally expected to be bread-winners. But we have seen changes within some classes of families and women who now give men money to come and marry them, some even sponsor their husbands in school and businesses, and some even take care of the financial burden fo the family without waiting for the husband. But our society frowns at it because it is not our tradition. Though the truth is that this changes are growing into our society and is rapidly affecting our traditions such that no man now want to marry a woman who totally depends on a man (Male, 53 years, businessman, interviewed on 24th July, 2023).

Gathered information show that there is great change in the tradition of who is to be a bread-winner among Ibibio married couples in Akwa Ibom State. Though the change has set within the elite class and is gradually taking root among the poor class such that no man want to marry any woman who believes in the ideology of total dependency on a man as a bread winner.

Gender Roles relatively to House Chores among the Ibibio Married Couples

In a traditional Ibibio society, a woman is found worthy of marriage when she was socialized with capacity to handle house chores effectively. Gathered data revealed that the fattening house was a process of preparation for effective house chores by young girls who were getting ready for marriage. Narratives from study participants show that among the Ibibio people of Akwa Ibom State, southern Nigeria, house chores is traditionally a woman's responsibility such that girls are socialized accordingly. One of the study participants in her narratives reported that;

House work is women's work and in the days of mbopo (fattening house) every young girl who was ready or parent were consulted for marriage, was sent to the fattening home where adult women will teach her the basic things she must know about marriage, like how to take care of her husband, satisfy her husband and how to do house work very well. These were qualifications for marriage. Though there have been changes today, but the fact that a woman must know how to do house work has not change. Therefore, what makes a woman a complete woman is her ability to do house work. House work is not for

men. If you allow a man to do the house work then there is no value for the woman (Female, 43 years, farmer, interviewed on 23rd July, 2023)

Another study participant from Uruan in his narrative reported that:

House chores are women responsibility and if you observe properly, you will realize that what I am talking about is residence within our culture. Like now, you will see that if a woman puts to birth a girl child, that child will be socialized by her parent in the traditional pattern of women responsibilities which include taking care of the house chores. As this child grows, you will observe that she start cooking with sand and later wash the tins she used with sand to depicts washing. So, house chores are for women though there have been changes these days, but the pattern still remains (Male, 56 years, businessman, interviewed on 17th July, 2023).

Gathered data also revealed that there are growing changes in the gender roles among the Ibibio people. House chores is not necessarily a woman role, because the couple can decide to employ cooks, housekeepers or a maid who either assist the wife in the house chores role or take complete responsibility of the roles. One of the study participants in her responses reported that;

My dear, gone are the days when they used to say a woman must cook for her husband, a woman must wash her husband's cloth, a woman must do this, must do that for her husband. Today, technology has helped us with washing machines to wash our husband's cloths and thank God the market women now help to slice the vegetables and get other things for cooking prepared for us in order to make it easy to cook else how do you explain that the woman will go to work or her business and return late in the evening tired in the quest to help the family and husband with financial assistance, then you expect her to come and cook at that hour. We now employ cooks where necessary and house keeper to help us with house chores. So the tradition of allocating house chores for women is no more a thing of celebration in our society today (Female, 56 years, business woman, interviewed on 24th July, 2023).

Gathered data through interview presents influence of modernization on the changing roles among married couples. In term of changes in house chores role, some women still believe that it is their responsibility to attend to some of the most important parts of the house chores despite changes in other parts of the role. For instance, a study participant in her narrative explained that;

I may have assistants in term of housekeeping, cooking, washing of clothes and others but, I am still responsible of washing my husband undies and cooking what he eats when I am around or supervising what is cooked for my husband and how his undies are washed. I do not leave any of those roles for assistant completely. I must know what is going on, how things are done for us and how values are given to us

for the money we pay for their assistants (Female, 43 years, business woman, interviewed on 17th July, 2023).

Another study participant has this to say during interview session;

Don't let anybody take the truth away from the fact. The truth is that house work is for women and not for men. No matter how changes want to affect it, it will still remain that way because it was fixed from the beginning and I believe it is across every ethnic group. Okay, when women started going to get house help because they now work or go out for business to assist or take care of some financial issues in the family, their husband now turn to the house help who does the house work and what we hear now is that house girls are snatching husbands. Okay, they went for male house help; we are now hearing madam is giving Oga food to cook or gateman. So, to me, this truth that house work is for women should remain and if changes are coming in as we see today, we should be careful about them to reduce problem among couple (Male, 44 years, and businessman, interviewed on 24th July, 2023).

House chores are social roles that are ascribed to women in traditional Ibibio society. The influence of modernization has brought about variety of changes in this set of role. Gathered data show that, the majority of Ibibio men go to capable extent in order to assist their wives attain success in this role. Though there are some forms of conflict in this role among the rich and the poor classes in Ibibio society, the people still accept the fact that it is the wife's responsibility to take care of the house chores whether by herself or by supervision of the assistant got for her or gotten by herself for the role.

Gender Roles relatively to Leadership among the Ibibio Married Couples

Leadership is said to be the man's role, and the world history has only witnessed very few women stepping into leadership roles. Among married couple in Ibibio society, men are expected to lead their wives and not vice versa. Since culture is dynamic, gathered data has revealed that there has been changes in this role. Study participants agreed through narratives on the changes which are observable today in leadership role among married couples in the Ibibio society. One of the key informants in his responses reported that:

Men were supposed to lead their wives and their family members in this our community, but the situation is not the same as of today. Our society is filled with so many changes that are pushing our people away from the right path. Today, you will see many women are leading their husband because they are the bread-winners of their families and their husband has no choice but to be answerable to them. Now a days, our young men are becoming lazier and the women are fighting to support their children. I can tell you today, many women are the one paying their children school fees and the men are just bossing themselves around. It is only few God fearing women that are bread-

winner of the family and are not ruling their husbands. My dear, we are seeing many different things in our society these days. Things are no longer the same again (Male, 50 years, business woman, interviewed on 24th July, 2023).

Another study participant in her narratives explained that;

We don't wait for men anymore. Gone are the days we women used to wait for men to bring everything. Today, we have decided to stand up for ourselves and our children, and if the father wants to take care of his responsibility let him be and if he doesn't, fine. But no man will have the boldness to talk about leading a woman when you cannot take care of her needs and that of your children. That is why you see today in our society it is as if we women are leading our husbands, no, we are just saying to the men that leading is by example and if you have no providing example stay off, let us help ourselves and our children for God's sake (Female, 33 years, business woman, interviewed on 17th July, 2023).

Data gathered through interview also revealed that most of the Ibibio married couples are running open leadership marriage and family where everyone is free to decide what he or she wants to do provided he or she has the capacity in terms of finance to bear the cost and consequences of such decision. A study participant in his narrative explained that;

Today's women are very strong and agile, they went to school, some of them are into great businesses and are making good money. As a husband, if she wants to run the home when you know that she can take care of the funding why should you disturb her? What is leadership without money? It is the person that has the money that should pioneer taking decisions because the person can fund the decisions. So as a man, if you have such a woman, you are blessed. So let her lead while you follow and your house will be at peace. Period (Male, 47 years, business woman, interviewed on 23rd July, 2023).

Power relations between Ibibio married couples has change from what was traditional among the Ibibio people. Men were culturally positioned to lead their wives through the traditional marriage rites which positioned the women as the man's subject or property, which directly puts the wife under the husband. Data gathered through interview revealed that there has been changes which is greatly influenced by the wave of modernization and economic dynamics. Today, a lot of women, are said to be leading their spouses and they are running their homes with the circumstantial permission of their husbands.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Emergence from analysis of gathered data revealed that there have been changes in gender roles among married couples in Ibibio land, Akwa Ibom State, South-South, Nigeria. Findings of the study revealed that men are traditionally and culturally the bread-winners for every family but modernization is believed to have cause a shift in the gender roles among married couples in Ibibio land. Facts arising from the analysis of data shown that, despite the

traditional and cultural belief which ascribed the role of bread-winners to men, there are changes in this traditional setting which have placed some women as bread-winners among married couples in Ibibio society. The dependency of women on men as bread-winners has undergone changes within the Ibibio society. Data revealed that most of the Ibibio women no longer depend on men or wait for men's financial supply as bread-winners. Ibibio women are known to be hardworking and capable of financial independence and many of the Ibibio women are not just bread-winners, but they pay children school fees and manage their husbands' financial needs. These findings disagree with Balgar (2018) who posited that in modern societies, because women are not paid for their house works, their works began to be seen as unnecessary, and men show themselves as bread winner.

Relating to house chores as gender role, findings of the study revealed that house work or house chores were traditionally reserved for women and it was a qualification for choosing a good wife for any groom. The situation according to findings of the study is not the same as at today. There is change in the house chore as gender role. It has been discovered through the study that most Ibibio men now assist their wives in handling house chores by making sure that their wives have assistant either by the husbands themselves or through provision of house helps, washing machine and other forms of assistants in order to make house chores easier for their wives.

Analysis of gathered data show that among the Ibibio people of Akwa Ibom State, southern Nigeria, the leadership role is ascribed to the husband among married couples. Modernization and its influential impact according to some of the gathered data, has created changes on many aspects of gender roles among married couples among the Ibibio people. Analysis of findings reveal that women have acquired financial capacity to lead the affairs of the couples, and this has positioned some of the women in the leadership role. Findings also revealed that some Ibibio men have adjusted to the changes in leadership role, especially those whose wives have acquired more financial power than their husband.

CONCLUSION

The definition of marriage has evolved due to the changes in the cultural structure of the various societies in the world today. Among the Ibibio people of Akwa Ibom State, South-South Nigeria, marriage is a relationship between man and woman who have passed through acceptable traditional rites of passage. Ibibio people culturally ascribe certain roles to the man and woman respectively. Gender roles in marriage are culturally ascribed to define the responsibilities of the husband and the wife. There have been changes in gender roles among the Ibibio people of Akwa Ibom State. Though being a bread-winner was traditionally ascribed to men, today, Ibibio women are taking responsibility of the role as they have chosen not to continually depend on or wait on men. House chores is gender role that was traditionally ascribed to women, it is now experiencing changes as Ibibio men are making sure that they assist their wives, and with the help of modernization, some of the Ibibio men now made provision for machines to assist their wives, with house helps. Despite the assistance given to the women for house chores, most of the women found it necessary to supervise what is going on in their houses. Leadership among the married couples has shifted from what were traditionally men's affairs to an open affair among married couples which

provides opportunity for women to also lead and take decisions in their homes.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the analysis of data, the following recommendations are proposed by the researcher;

1. There is a saying that what a man can do, a woman can do also provided she has the capacity to do so. This implies that women should be allowed to make provision for the family as bread-winners when they have capacity to do so.
2. Married couples should understand marriage as a union which anyone should be capable to help especially when it comes to house chores provided the party has the capacity to do so.
3. Married couples should be ready to adopt positive changes provided such are able to bring progress and efficiency to the union and the family.
4. Leadership should be understood from the point of humility whereby the man remains the head of the union and the woman follows accordingly, but with readiness of the couple to be humble to listen and receive each partner's contribution when necessary.
5. Married couples should be able to employ technological provisions from modernization positively within their capacity to make house chores easy and their home enjoyable.

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